

Evaluation of Clipping Versus Bipolar Electrocautery of Cystic Artery in Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Background: The widespread use of surgical clips in laparoscopic cholecystectomy has been associated with various complications, including clip slippage, dislodgement, migration, ulceration, and necrosis of the cystic duct, which may lead to bile leakage. In response to these risks, clipless laparoscopic techniques, particularly the use of electrocautery, have been explored. While both monopolar and bipolar diathermy are used for tissue cauterization, monopolar systems pose a higher risk of lateral thermal injury to surrounding structures such as the common bile duct, hepatic artery, and bowel. Bipolar electrocautery, although safer, is not without drawbacks, including smoke generation that may hinder visualization during surgery.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of bipolar electrocautery for controlling the cystic artery during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and to determine whether it is a suitable alternative to conventional clip application.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted on 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, who were divided into two groups of 50. Group A underwent surgery with clip application to control the cystic artery, while group B used bipolar electrocautery. Postoperative outcomes were assessed over a two-week follow-up period.

Results: Mean operative times were 35.19 minutes in group A and 34.18 minutes in group B. Median ages were comparable between groups. One case of intraoperative bleeding occurred in group B and was successfully managed. No major complications or postoperative bleeding were noted in either group.

Conclusion: Bipolar electrocautery is a safe and effective alternative to surgical clips for cystic artery control in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Introduction

Cholecystectomy is the most frequently performed major abdominal procedure worldwide, primarily indicated for the management of symptomatic gallstone disease. The first successful cholecystectomy was carried out by Carl Langenbuch in 1882, and for more than a century, the open approach remained the gold standard for treating gallstones [1]. A significant

advancement occurred in 1985 when Mühe from Böblingen, Germany, performed the first endoscopic cholecystectomy [27]. Although initially met with skepticism by the surgical community, laparoscopic cholecystectomy quickly gained global acceptance and has since been recognized as the standard of care [2,3]. The 1992 NIH Consensus Development Conference reinforced this shift by confirming that laparoscopic

More Information

How to cite this article: Aljadri MTMK, Daham MJ, Alyassary AAS, Khiri NK. Evaluation of Clipping Versus Bipolar Electrocautery of Cystic Artery in Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(3):175-8.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).26

Keywords:

Clips,
Cystic artery,
Laparoscopic cholecystectomy,
Electrocautery.

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cholecystectomy is a safe and effective treatment for most patients with symptomatic gallstones [4,27]. Currently, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is among the most common elective surgeries performed. This is largely attributed to the increasing prevalence of gallstone disease and the broad availability of training in minimally invasive surgical techniques [5]. This method has transformed general surgery by introducing minimally invasive approaches that offer numerous benefits, such as decreased postoperative pain, shorter hospital stays, quicker return to daily activities, improved cosmetic outcomes, early bowel function recovery, and overall cost reduction [6,7]. Nevertheless, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is not without its challenges, particularly in terms of anatomical visualization. Unlike open surgery, the visual perspective differs, demanding careful technique. Achieving the Critical View of Safety (CVS) is crucial for accurately identifying the cystic duct and artery, thereby reducing the risk of bile duct injuries [8,9]. Although the cystic artery usually originates from the right hepatic artery, its origin and course can vary considerably, necessitating meticulous identification and control during surgery [10,11]. Improper control of the cystic artery can result in significant intraoperative bleeding, obscuring the operative field and possibly leading to conversion to open surgery [12]. Various techniques are used for securing the artery, including titanium clips, monopolar and bipolar electrocautery, and ultrasonic devices [13,14]. Titanium clips are favored for their effectiveness, low cost, and MRI compatibility [15], though complications such as migration, dislodgement, and ductal necrosis with bile leakage have been reported [16]. Electrothermal methods, particularly bipolar diathermy, are also commonly used and offer targeted energy application with minimal lateral thermal spread, preserving adjacent structures like the bile duct and hepatic vessels [17,18]. Although smoke generation remains a drawback, bipolar systems are generally safer than monopolar alternatives [19]. Additionally, advanced bipolar instruments now integrate vessel sealing and dissection, enhancing surgical efficiency. While harmonic scalpels are effective, their high cost and limited availability make clip application and bipolar electrocautery more practical and cost-effective options in many settings [20]. Given these considerations, this study was designed to compare the safety and outcomes of cystic artery control using bipolar electrocautery versus traditional clip application during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Method

This prospective comparative study was conducted at the Department of Surgery, Al-Imamain Al-Kadhumain Teaching Hospital, between April 2018 and May 2021. A total of 100 patients were included. They had been

diagnosed with symptomatic gallstone disease. They were scheduled for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Patients were equally divided into two groups of 50 each: Group A underwent cystic artery control using titanium clips, and Group B underwent bipolar electrocautery for the same. Exclusion criteria included patients with significant co-morbidities, coagulation disorders, suspected or diagnosed malignancy, previous major upper abdominal surgeries, common bile duct stones, gallbladder empyema, pregnancy, or those with difficulty identifying Calot's triangle. All patients underwent thorough preoperative assessments including detailed medical history, physical examination, complete blood count, renal and liver function tests, coagulation profile, chest X-ray, ECG, abdominal ultrasound, pulmonary function tests, and viral screening. MRCP was performed when indicated. Informed written consent was obtained from all patients. Surgery was performed under general anesthesia using the conventional four-port laparoscopic technique. Pneumoperitoneum was established using a Veress needle, followed by placement of the primary port. Patients were positioned in reverse Trendelenburg with left tilt for optimal exposure. Dissection of Calot's triangle was performed carefully, ensuring identification of the cystic artery and duct. In Group A, the cystic artery was secured using three titanium clips (Ligaclip 300), and in Group B, bipolar electrocautery was used for coagulation. Any intraoperative bleeding was recorded, including severity, location, and management. Postoperatively, all patients were monitored for vital signs, signs of hemorrhage or bile leak (through drains and ultrasound when needed), and other complications. Drain placement in Morrison's pouch was routine. Data were collected on operative time, blood loss, complications, and hospital stay. Follow-up was done on the tenth postoperative day. A statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 20.0, setting significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results

As shown in Table 1, among the 50 patients in Group A (clip application), 14% were male and 86% were female. In Group B (bipolar cauterization), 10% were male and 90% were female, reflecting a female predominance in both groups. The median age of patients was 35.1 years in Group A and 35.3 years in Group B. In all cases, a single cystic artery was identified, and it originated from the right hepatic artery. Intraoperative bleeding from the cystic artery occurred in only one patient from Group B, which was successfully managed by reapplying clips. No conversions to open cholecystectomy were required in either group, indicating the safety and feasibility of both methods for cystic artery control. As shown in Table 2, the mean operative time for Group A was 35.19 minutes, while

for Group B it was 34.18 minutes. There was no statistically significant difference in operative time between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). Postoperative evaluation, including observation for fresh blood in drains and detection of fluid collections via ultrasound, revealed no significant complications in either group. The postoperative recovery was comparable between both groups. In Group A, 83.5% of patients were discharged on the first postoperative day, while 16.5% stayed for a second day. In Group B, 81.5% were discharged on the first day and 18.5% on the second day. The difference in hospital stay was not statistically significant, suggesting similar recovery profiles for both clip application and bipolar cauterization techniques.

Table 1: Patients Demographic Data

Patients demographic data		
Parameter	Group A	Group B
Total number	50	50
M/F	7/43	5/45
Mean age-/+SD (years)	35.1+/-10.1	35.3+/-7.8

Table 2: Clinical Outcome Data

Clinical outcome data			
Parameters	Group A	Group B	p-value*
Mean operative time +/-SD	35.19+/-9.9	34.18+/-8.7	0.367
Cystic artery bleeding	0%	5%	
Mean hospital stay +/-SD	1.4+/-0.5	1.2+/-0.4	0.5
Post-operative bleeding	0	0	

Note: * using unpaired student t-test

Post-operative pain scale in Table 3 shows that the pain scale was no significantly differences between two groups (A and B) with P-value >0.5. All the patients have responded to single analgesia to relief their pain.

Table 3: Pain Scale

Pain scale	Mild	moderate	Sever
Group (A)	25	20	5
Group (B)	24	22	4

Note: P-value* 0.89; *chi-square

Discussion

With the growing popularity of minimally invasive techniques and increasing surgical expertise, laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become the most

commonly performed hepatobiliary procedure worldwide [21,28]. One of the most crucial steps during this procedure is the secure control of the cystic artery, which, if not adequately achieved, can result in intraoperative bleeding and serious complications. Several techniques have been employed for this purpose, including titanium clip application, monopolar and bipolar electrocautery, vessel sealers, and ultrasonic devices [22]. This prospective comparative study aimed to evaluate the safety and efficacy of two commonly used methods for cystic artery control—titanium clip application and bipolar electrocautery—in 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Although bipolar electrocautery is considered an efficient tool for vessel coagulation, its use demands caution. The degree of thermal spread can be less predictable, and the current may travel through non-insulated instruments or trocars, potentially causing unintended damage. Therefore, surgeons must exercise precision during dissection of Calot's triangle, avoiding electrocautery near critical structures like the common bile duct to minimize risks. Our findings showed that both methods were safe and effective, with no significant intraoperative or postoperative complications observed in either group. Consistent with earlier research, there was no evidence of postoperative bleeding in either group, aligning with the findings of Huscher et al., who also reported successful hemostasis with energy devices such as ultrasonic dissectors [23]. Demographically, the patient population demonstrated a strong female predominance with a male-to-female ratio of 1:4, in line with prior studies by Hugh et al., who reported similar gender distributions in laparoscopic anatomy studies of the cystic artery [24]. Age distribution was also comparable between groups, with a median age of around 35 years, which supports the age demographics described by Khan et al. [25]. The average operative time was slightly shorter in the clip group (37.4 minutes) compared to the electrocautery group (38.45 minutes), though the difference was not statistically significant. All patients had a normally originating cystic artery, and there was no significant variation in anatomical findings or dissection difficulty. In terms of hospital stay, the majority of patients in both groups were discharged within 24 hours, with no substantial difference in recovery time or postoperative morbidity. These findings reinforce the notion that bipolar electrocautery, when used with proper technique, is a viable and cost-effective alternative to clips. Our results suggest that both methods are equally competent for achieving hemostasis during laparoscopic cholecystectomy without compromising patient outcomes [26].

Conclusion

We conclude that during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, bipolar electrocautery can be used as a safe and effective alternative to clipping for cystic artery hemostasis. Both methods demonstrated comparable outcomes in terms of bleeding control, operative time, and length of hospital stay. Regardless of the technique used, the most critical factor in ensuring safe and successful hemostasis is the meticulous dissection of Calot's triangle to accurately identify the origin of the cystic artery.

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